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Investigating the Effect of Biogas Slurry on the Morpho-Physiological Traits of Mustard Plant

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ABSTRACT

Mustard plant is an herbaceous annual plant belonging to a Brassicaceae family. Salt stress is a major environmental stress that affects plant growth and development. The aim of this research is to investigate the effect of biogas slurry on the morpho-physiological traits of mustard plant under salt stress. The experiment consisted of four levels of salinity stress (0mM, 50mM, 100mM, 150mM) and three level of biogas slurry per pot (0 g, 20 g, 40 g) in a completely randomized design with three replicates. An appropriate statistical tool was used to analyze the data by using COSTAT software. The results indicated that morphological parameters decreased with increasing NaCl stress (50mM, 100mM, 150mM) but biogas slurry (20g,40g) mitigated the negative effect. Physiological parameters also decreased with increasing NaCl stress (50mM, 100mM, 150mM) but biogas slurry (20g, 40g) reduced the effect of stress. In case of ion analysis Na^+ content increased with increasing NaCl stress,

biogas slurry reduced Na^+ uptake in mustard. In case of K^+ and Ca^{2+} increased with increasing NaCl stress (50mM, 100mM, 150mM), biogas slurry treated plants maintained higher K^+ and Ca^{2+} level. In case of antioxidant enzyme, increased with increasing NaCl stress, biogas slurry further increased enzyme activity, indicating improved stress tolerance. H_2O_2 and MDA content increased with increasing stress. Biogas slurry reduced H_2O_2 and MDA content under stress, indicating decreased oxidative stress.

INTRODUCTION

Among the key oilseed Brassica crops is rapeseed mustard. Within this category. Indian mustard (*Brassica juncea* L.) is a significant edible crop that yields oil, accounting for almost 90% of the planted area in India dedicated to brassica oilseeds (Rai *et al.*, 2022). After palm oil and soybean oil is the globe's third-largest supplier of vegetable oil. Due to its consistent correlation with other significant abiotic stresses like salt and high temperatures, drought stress is acknowledged as the primary driver of the reduction in agricultural productivity (Kopecka *et al.*, 2023). It is predicted that the percentage of areas susceptible to drought will have doubled by the end of the twenty-first century (Chen *et al.*, 2025).

The NaCl stress has a direct impact on the growth biomass and yield of the plant, which result in a significant reduction in the amount of minerals that the plants are able to absorb (Kumari *et al.*, 2022). It is the continuous exposure to salinity that causes secondary stress, also known as oxidative stress, which results in the production of reactive oxygen species (ROS) that are harmful to biomolecules such as proteins, nucleic acids (DNA/RNA), membrane lipids, and other similar substances (Fariha *et al.*, 2025).

Salt stress is a significant abiotic stressor, approximately 20% of all cultivated soils and 33% of irrigated agricultural soils worldwide are impacted by elevated salt levels in the soil (Basak *et al.*, 2022). Furthermore, several factors such as the erosion of natural rocks, inadequate farming methods, limited rainfall, irrigation with salty water, and excessive surface evaporation are contributing to the expansion of the salt-affected area of the world at an annual rate of 10%. (El Sabagh *et al.*, 2020).

Salinity induces hyper ionic and hyperosmotic stressors, ultimately causing the death of plants (Muhammad Nabeel Sharif *et al.*, 2025). Elevated salinity levels can also cause damage to the plant cells, resulting in the suppression of growth. Salinity induces harmful consequences within the plant. Accumulation of salts in the mature leaves can lead to their demise (Karthika and Parvathi, 2018). The elevated salinity levels adversely affect the spiral growth and cortical microtubule arrangement in *Arabidopsis* plants, resulting in water scarcity-induced stress (Gupta *et al.*, 2022). The interactions among salts can result in imbalances and deficiencies of minerals. Other repercussions of salt stress include the closure of stomata, which limits the loss of water, reduces the fixation of carbon dioxide (CO_2), and increases the formation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) (Zahra *et al.*, 2022).

Biogas slurry is formed from this process (Chauhan *et al.*, 2020). It contains essential elements like phosphorus and potassium necessary for crop growth, as well as trace elements like iron, manganese, and zinc (Nardin and Francioso, 2021). The transformation of biogas sludge into fertilizer has the potential to reduce the risks the

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environment faces. It is possible to apply biogas slurry to crops as a direct fertilizer, or it can be combined with other organic elements and synthetic fertilizers (Kumar *et al.*, 2022).

Currently, a variety of food crops, including wheat, rice, maize, vegetables like lettuce, Chinese leeks, and Chinese cabbage, and fruits like apples, utilize biogas slurry as a fertilizer (Wang *et al.*, 2023). This improves the carbon/nitrogen (C/N) ratio in the slurry that provides easily nutrient availability to plants and soil biota (Li *et al.*, 2022). The biogas slurry is composed of 93% water and 7% dry matter, with 4.5% organic matter and 2.5% inorganic matter being the components that make up the dry matter (Rabiya Javaid *et al.*, 2025). Phosphorus, potassium, zinc, iron, manganese, and copper are further elements that can be found in the digested biogas slurry. Many of these elements have been depleted from the soil as a result of intensive farming methods. In addition, biogas slurry can be utilized to cultivate healthy and rich soil for the purpose of crop cultivation (Kumar *et al.*, 2022).

It is noteworthy that *Brassica juncea* L. is vulnerable to salt stress, which impairs crop productivity and, therefore, oil output. One of the long-term methods for enhancing *Brassica juncea* L. health under salinity stress is the use of beneficial bacteria (Liang *et al.*, 2023). During NaCl stress, mustard plants' stability of membranes (lipid peroxidation) is disrupted by the production of ROS (H_2O_2) (Islam *et al.*, 2025). In mustard plants, the protective properties of both non-enzymatic as well as enzymatic antioxidants are investigated both with and without NaCl. Keeping in view the above discussion, the purpose of the proposed study is to investigate how various concentrations of biogas slurry affect the morpho-physiological characteristics of mustard under salinity stress (Kabeyi and Olanrewaju, 2022).

METHODOLOGY

Experimental Design

The experimental pots were leveled and prepared. The biogas slurry must be mixed with soil. Mustard seeds were sown in these pots. Biogas slurry provides a considerable quantity of potassium and phosphorus in addition to nitrogen. After 40 days of development, the plants taken and examined for growth. Salt stress was induced by using four level 0mM, 500mM, 100mM, 150Mm and three level of biogas slurry 0g, 20g, 40g was applied to mitigate the effect of stress on mustard. Hoagland's nutrient solution was applied to each pot on a weekly basis throughout the experiment. Seven seeds were grown in every pot and later moistened with distilled water. Initially, all pots were maintained at the same water level to achieve maximum growth and development. Further watering was done according to the experiment requirement. The study applied factor A, which consisted of three levels of biogas slurry (0g, 20g and 40g) and factor B, which consisted of four levels of stress (0mM, 50mM, 100mM, 1500mM). Two plants were carefully removed from each pot a few days after treatment for data collection.

Morphological Parameters

Leaf width (cm)

A measuring tape was used to find the leaf's width. To measure the leaf thickness, a fresh, fully grown leaf with no spots was chosen from each plant.

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Leaf length (cm)

One healthy, usually sixth leaf with a smooth, shiny surface was used to measure the width of the leaf. It was decided to look at nine plants from each reproduction. The measuring stick was used to get the leaf's length.

Number of leaves

It was possible to find the average by counting the amount of leaves on each plant.

Root Length (cm)

One plant from each copy was pulled out by its root, and its length was measured on a scale. The average of these measurements was then found.

Shoot Length (cm)

One plant was uprooted and shoot length was measured by using a measuring scale and their mean was calculated.

Fresh Root Weight (g)

One plant from each replication was uprooted carefully and roots were separated from each plant. Roots were washed out, cleaned, and their fresh weight was measured by using weighting balance.

Fresh Shoot Weight(g)

From each copy, one plant was taken out and cleaned. Then, a weighting balance was used to find out how much each plant's fresh shoot weighed.

Dry Root Weight(g)

One Plant from each replication was uprooted, roots were separated and dried in Right for few hours to remove humidity. Then the roots were fully dried in oven at 18PC. After this each plant root dry weight was measured by using weighting balance.

Dry shoot Weight(g)

Shoots were dried out completely in a 100°C oven. After this each plant shoot's dry weight was measured by using weighting balance

Physiological Parameters

Photosynthetic Pigments

0.5 g of that leaf was ground into mortal and pestles. After that, 5 ml of 80% acetone was added to the extract, and it was left at 10°C for one night. The next day, the extract was spun at 14,000 rpm for five minutes. A spectrophotometer was used to test the absorbance of the supernatant at three different wavelengths: 480nm, 645nm, and 663nm for carotenoids, chlorophyll b, and chlorophyll.

Biochemical Parameters

Digestion Method

Each plant's Ig dry root was broken down in digestion flasks with 2ml of pure H₂SO₄ at room temperature. Then, 4 ml of 35% H.O. was added to the flask, and it was boiled at 350°C until the solution lost its color. Once this solution was clean, 50ml of pure water was added to thin it out. The flame photometer was used to check this mixture and find out how many ions were in it.

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Biochemical parameters

Super oxide dismutase Activity (SOD)

Crush 0.25 grams of fresh leaves into a fine powder. Five milliliters of a 50-millimolar potassium phosphate buffer solution should be dispensed. For fifteen minutes, spin the sample at 14,000 turns per minute in a centrifuge. Twenty millimolars (mM) of potassium phosphate buffer should be added to a solution. Each of the 250 ml of pure water should have 8.7 g of K₂HPO₄ and 6.8 g of KH₂PO₄ dissolved in it. Separate the ingredients and mix them separately. Then, add the two mixtures together to get a 500-ml solution with a pH of 7.4. Put 50 µl of buffer and 50 µl of pure water into a test tube to make a blank solution. Add riboflavin to the other cuvettes after you've added it to the blank one. Put it in light for 15 minutes and then use a spectrophotometer to look at it. The reaction mixture is made up of 400 µl of pure water, 250 µl of 200 mM KP buffer, 100 µl of L. methionine, 100 µl of Triton, 50 µl of NBT, 50 µl of enzyme extract, and 50 µl of riboflavin. Next, find the absorbance at 560 nm. Make sure the blank number is higher than the samples before you record it.

Peroxidase activity (POD)

Crush 0.25 grams of fresh leaves into a fine powder. Give out five milliliters of a potassium phosphate buffer solution with a 50-millimolar concentration. For fifteen minutes, spin the sample at 14,000 turns per minute in a centrifuge. 20 millimolars (mM) of potassium phosphate buffer should be added to a solution. Separate 8.7 grams of K₂HPO₄ and 6.8 grams of KH₂PO₄ and mix them in 250 milliliters of pure water. First mix the items one at a time, and then mix them all together until you have a 500-ml mixture with a pH of 7.4. Make a potassium phosphate buffer solution with a strength of 50 mM. 50 ml of purified water should be added to 750 µl of Guaiacol to make it less concentrated. 100 microliters of hydrogen peroxide, which is 22.8 microliters for every 5 milliliters of water and Make a solution with 50 microliters of enzyme extract and 100 microliters of a material. Find the absorbance at 450 nanometers in length and width.

Catalase activity (CAT)

Take 0.25 grams of fresh leaves and grind it. Place 5 milliliters of a solution containing Potassium phosphate buffer at a concentration of 50 millimolar. Put the sample to centrif-ugation at a speed of 14000 revolutions per minute for a duration of 15 minutes. Create a solution of Potassium phosphate buffer at a concentration of 20 millimolar (mM). Each time, mix 8.7 g of K₂HPO₄ and 6.8 g of KH₂PO₄ with 250 ml of pure water. Mix the two mixtures individually, and then mix them together to make a 500-ml mixture with a pH of 7.4. Measure out 29 µl of H₂O₂ and put it into falcon tubes to make a solution with a concentration of 0.059 M. Until the volume hits 5 ml, thin the solution with clean water. Cover with aluminum foil. Add 1.9 ml of KP buffer (50mM), 100 µl of H₂O₂ (0.059 M), and 100 µl of enzyme extract to a test tube. Then, measure the absorbance at 240 nm. Di-potassium hydrogen phosphate (also called dipotassium phosphate) has the chemical formula (12), as does potassium di-hydrogen phosphate (also called mono potassium phosphate) with the formula (27).

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Hydrogen peroxide, which has the chemical formula H₂O₂, and distilled water are also used.

Statistical analysis

The COSTAT tools were used to look at the data from three replications. Also, the least significant difference (LSD) was used to compare the treatment means at the 5% level of likelihood.

RESULTS

Root Length(cm)

The bar graph describes the average root lengths under varying NaCl concentrations (0mM, 50mM, 100mM, and 150mM) and slurry treatments (0 g, 20 g, and 40 g). Increased slurry amounts positively influence root length across all NaCl concentrations. The interaction effect is particularly noticeable at 50mM and 150mM NaCl, where higher slurry treatments mitigate the stress-induced reduction in root length. This suggests that slurry application can enhance root growth even under saline conditions, highlighting its potential as a beneficial agricultural practice.

Figure 1- Effect of biogas slurry on root length (cm) of mustard under salt stress

Shoot Length(cm)

The bar graph describes the average root lengths under varying NaCl concentrations (0mM, 50mM, 100mM, and 150mM) and slurry treatments (0 g, 20 g, and 40 g). The interaction effect is particularly noticeable at 50mM and 150mM NaCl, where higher slurry treatments mitigate the stress-induced reduction in root length. This suggests that slurry application can enhance root growth even under saline conditions, highlighting its potential as a beneficial agricultural practice.

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Figure 2- Effect of biogas slurry on shoot length (cm) of mustard under salt stress

Root Fresh Weight (g)

At 0mM NaCl, the RFW is high and similar across all slurry treatments. As NaCl concentration increases, RFW generally decreases, but higher slurry amounts mitigate this reduction. Notably, at 150mM NaCl, the highest slurry amount (40g) results in the highest RFW compared to other slurry treatments, suggesting that higher slurry amounts can alleviate the negative effects of salt stress. Error bars indicate the variability and precision of the data, highlighting the reliability of the observed trends.

Figure 3- Effect of biogas slurry on root fresh weight (g) of mustard under salt stress

Root Dry Weight (g)

The RDW across different NaCl concentrations (0mM, 50mM, 100mM, and 150mM) and slurry amounts (0g, 20g, and 40g). At 0mM NaCl, the RDW is high and similar

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across all slurry treatments. As NaCl concentration increases, RDW generally decreases, but higher slurry amounts mitigate this reduction. Notably, at 150mM NaCl, the highest slurry amount (40g) results in the highest RDW compared to other slurry treatments, suggesting that higher slurry amounts can alleviate the negative effects of salt stress. Error bars indicate the variability and precision of the data, highlighting the reliability of the observed trends.

Figure 4- Effect of biogas slurry on root dry weight (g) of mustard under salt stress

Shoot Fresh Weight (g)

The SFW across different NaCl concentrations (0mM, 50mM, 100mM, and 150mM) and slurry amounts (0g, 20g, and 40g). At 0mM NaCl, the SFW is high and similar across all slurry treatments. As NaCl concentration increases, SFW generally decreases, but higher slurry amounts mitigate this reduction. Notably, at 150mM NaCl, the highest slurry amount (40g) results in the highest SFW compared to other slurry treatments, suggesting that higher slurry amounts can alleviate the negative effects of salt stress. Error bars indicate the variability and precision of the data, highlighting the reliability of the observed trends.

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Figure 5- Effect of biogas slurry on shoot fresh weight (g) of mustard under salt stress

Shoot Dry Weight (g)

At 0mM NaCl, the SDW is high and similar across all slurry treatments. As NaCl concentration increases, SDW generally decreases, but higher slurry amounts mitigate this reduction. Notably, at 150mM NaCl, the highest slurry amount (40g) results in the highest SDW compared to other slurry treatments, suggesting that higher slurry amounts can alleviate the negative effects of salt stress. Error bars indicate the variability and precision of the data, highlighting the reliability of the observed trends.

Figure 6- Effect of biogas slurry on shoot dry weight (g) of mustard under salt stress

Plant Height (cm)

Impact of varying salt concentration (0mM, 50mM, 100mM, 150mM) and slurry amounts (0g, 20g, 40g) on plant height. The bar chart shows that shoot dry weight is

highest at 0mM salt stress and decrease with increasing NaCl concentration. However, higher slurry amounts consistently result in higher plant height across all salt stress levels. At 0mM NaCl, all slurry treatments yield similar plant height. As salt concentration increases to 50mM and 100mM plant height decreased but remains higher with increased slurry amounts. At the highest NaCl concentration (150mM), the plant height is lowest, yet the 40g slurry treatment shows a significant mitigating effect, resulting in the highest plant height among the treatment.

Figure 7- Effect of biogas slurry on plant height (cm) of mustard under salt stress

No. of Leaves

As the level of salinity stress increased, there was a corresponding decrease in the no of leaves of each plant. Nevertheless, the impact of salinity was alleviated by applying biogas slurry with the concentrations of 0g, 20g, and 40g being arranged in sequence. Consequently, biogas slurry emerged as a pivotal growth regulator for maize, adding in its adaptation to the adverse effects of salinity stress.

Figure 8- Effect of biogas slurry on no. of leaves of mustard under salt stress

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Leaf Area

The bar chart shows that leaf area is highest at 0mM NaCl and decreases with increasing NaCl concentration. However, higher slurry amounts consistently result in higher leaf area across all NaCl levels. At 0mM NaCl, all slurry treatments yield similar leaf area. As NaCl concentration increases to 50mM and 100mM, leaf area declines but remains higher with increased slurry amounts. At the highest NaCl concentration (150mM), the leaf area is lowest, yet the 40g slurry treatment shows a significant mitigating effect, resulting in the highest leaf area among the treatments.

Figure 9- Effect of biogas slurry on leaf area of mustard under salt stress

Chlorophyll a (mg / g)

Chlorophyll a content in mustard plants under different NaCl stress levels (0mM, 50mM, 100mM, and 150mM) and varying slurry concentrations (0g, 20g and 40g). At each stress level, the chlorophyll a content generally increases with higher slurry concentrations. Chlorophyll a content in mustard plants under different lead stress levels (0mM, 50mM, 100mM, 150mM) and varying slurry concentrations (0g, 20g, 40g). At each stress level, the chlorophyll a content generally increases with higher slurry concentrations. For instance, at 0mM lead stress the chlorophyll rises as slurry concentration increases from 0g to 40g. This trend is consistent across all stress levels, although the overall chlorophyll a content decreased as lead stress concentration increases, indicating a stress-induced reduction in chlorophyll a.

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Figure 10- Effect of biogas slurry on chl a of mustard under salt stress

Chlorophyll b (mg / g)

Chlorophyll b content in mustard plants under different NaCl stress levels (0mM, 50mM, 100mM, and 150mM) and varying slurry concentrations (0g, 20g and 40g). This trend is consistent across all stress levels, although the overall chlorophyll a content decreased as lead stress concentration increases, indicating a stress-induced reduction in chlorophyll b.

Figure 11- Effect of biogas slurry on chl b of mustard under salt stress

Carotenoids

At each stress level, the chlorophyll a content generally increases with higher slurry concentrations. For instance, at 0mM lead stress the chlorophyll rises as slurry concentration increases from 0g to 40g. Carotenoid content in mustard plants under varying levels of NaCl stress (0mM, 50mM, 100mM, and 150mM) and different

slurry concentrations (0g, 20g, and 40g). Across all NaCl stress levels, the carotenoid content tends to increase with higher slurry concentrations. For example, at 0mM NaCl, the content rises slurry concentration increases from 0g to 40g. At the highest stress level of 150mM NaCl, the carotenoid content is lowest, but still increases with higher slurry concentrations. These results suggest that slurry can mitigate some of the negative effects of NaCl stress on the carotenoid content in mustard plants.

Figure 12- Effect of biogas slurry on carotenoids of mustard under salt stress

Root K⁺ contents

Levels of K⁺ ions in the roots of mustard plants subjected to different NaCl stress levels (0mM, 50mM, 100mM, and 150mM) and varying slurry concentrations (0g, 20g, and 40g). At 0mM NaCl stress, K⁺ ion levels are highest, and they increase further with higher slurry concentrations, peaking at approximately K⁺ ions for the 40g slurry concentration. As NaCl stress increases to 50mM and 100mM, K ion levels decrease overall, but still show an upward trend with higher slurry concentrations. At the highest stress level of 150mM NaCl, K⁺ ion levels are the lowest, yet the beneficial effect of slurry is still evident, with higher concentrations of slurry relating with higher K⁺ ion levels.

Figure 13- Effect of biogas slurry on root K^+ content of mustard plant under salt stress

Shoot K^+ contents

Levels of K ions in the shoots of mustard plants subjected to Afferent NaCl stress levels (0mM, 50mM, 100mM, and 150mM) and varying slurry concentrations (0g, 20g, 40g). At 0mM NaCl stress, K^+ ion levels are highest, and they increase further with higher slurry concentrations. As NaCl stress increases to 50mM and 100mM, K^+ ion levels decrease overall, but still show an upward trend with higher slurry concentrations. At the highest stress level of 150mM NaCl, K^+ ion levels are the lowest, yet the beneficial effect of slurry is still evident, with higher concentrations of slurry correlating with higher K^+ ion levels. This graph suggests that while NaCl stress reduces K ion content in maize shoots, the application of slurry helps to mitigate this effect, promoting higher K^+ ion levels even under stress conditions.

Figure 14- Effect of biogas slurry on shoot K^+ content of mustard under salt stress

Root Ca^{2+} content

Concentration of Ca^{2+} ions in mustard roots subjected to different concentrations of NaCl stress (0mM, 50mM, 100mM, and 150mM) and varying amounts of slurry (0g, 20g, and 40g). At 0mM NaCl, Ca^{2+} ion concentration creases with the amount of slurry, with the highest concentration observed at 40g. As The NaCl concentration increases to 50mM and 100mM, a similar trend is observed where higher slurry amounts result in higher Ca ion concentrations, although the overall ion concentration decreases compared to the 0mM NaCl condition. At 150mM NaCl, the Ca^{2+} concentration is the lowest across all slurry treatments, but still shows an increasing trend with higher slurry amounts.

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Figure 15- Effect of biogas slurry on root Ca^{2+} content of mustard under salt stress

Shoot Ca^{2+} content

Concentration of Ca^{2+} ions in mustard shoots subjected to different concentrations of NaCl stress (0mM, 50mM, 100mM, and 150mM) and varying amounts of slurry (0g, 20g, and 40g). At 0mM NaCl, Ca^{2+} ion concentration increases with the amount of slurry, with the highest concentration observed at 40g. As the NaCl concentration increases to 50mM and 100mM, a similar trend is observed where higher slurry amounts result in higher Ca^{2+} ion concentrations, although the overall ion concentration decreases compared to the 0mM NaCl condition. At 150mM NaCl, the Ca^{2+} ion concentration is the lowest across all slurry treatments, but still shows an increasing trend with higher slurry amounts.

Figure 16- Effect of biogas slurry on shoot Ca^{2+} content of mustard under salt

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stress

Root Na⁺ content

Concentration of Na⁺ ions in the roots of maize plants under different conditions. The x-axis represents varying concentrations of a treatment (0mM, 50mM, 100mM, and 150mM), while the y-axis shows the number of Na⁺ ions. Different colored bars represent different amounts of a substance added (0 g, 20 g, and 40 g). The results indicate that as the concentration of the treatment increases, the Na⁺ ions in the roots also increase for all substance amounts. The highest Na⁺ ions concentration is observed at 150mM treatment with 40 g of substance, while the lowest is at 0mM treatment with 0 g of substance.

Figure 17- Effect of biogas slurry on root Na⁺ content of mustard plant under salt stress

Shoot Na⁺ content

Concentration of Na⁺ ions in the shoots of mustard plants under different conditions. The x-axis represents varying concentrations of a treatment (0mM, 50mM, 100mM, and 15 mM), while the y-axis shows the number of Na⁺ ions. Different colored bars represent different amounts of a substance added (0 g, 20 g, and 40 g). The results indicate that as the concentration of the treatment increases, the Na ions in the shoots also increase for all substance amounts. The highest Na⁺ ions concentration is observed at 150mM treatment with 40 g of substance, while the lowest is at 0mM treatment with 0 g of substance.

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Figure 18- Effect of biogas slurry on shoot Na⁺ content of mustard plant under salt stress

Peroxidase (POD)

Peroxidase (POD) activity in mustard plants subjected to various salt stress levels (0mM, 50mM, 100mM, 150mM) and different biogas slurry amounts (0g, 20g, 40g). POD activity is highest at 0mM salt stress and generally decreases as salt stress increases. Within each salt stress level, higher biogas slurry amounts tend to enhance POD activity, though the overall trend shows a decline in POD activity as salt stress intensifies. At the highest salt stress level (150mM), POD activity is the lowest across all biogas slurry treatments, suggesting that severe salt stress may overwhelm the plant's antioxidative defenses despite the nutrient benefits of biogas slurry.

Figure 19- Effect of biogas slurry on POD content of mustard plant under salt stress

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Super oxidase Dismutase (SOD)

Super oxidase Dismutase (SOD) activity in mustard plant subjected to various salt stress levels (0mM, 50mM, 100mM, 150mM) and different biogas slurry amounts (0g, 20g, 40g). SOD activity is highest at 0mM salt stress and generally decreases as salt stress increases. Within each salt stress level, higher biogas slurry amounts tend to enhance SOD activity, though the overall trend shows a decline in SOD activity as salt stress intensifies. At the highest salt stress level (150mM), SOD activity is the lowest across all biogas slurry treatments, suggesting that severe lead stress may overwhelm the plant's anti oxidative defenses despite the nutrient benefits of biogas slurry. This pattern highlights the complex interaction between nutrient supplementation and environmental stress in influencing plant biochemical responses.

Figure 20- Effect of biogas slurry on SOD of mustard plant under salt stress

CAT (Catalase)

Catalase (CAT) activity in mustard plants subjected to various salt stress levels (0mM, 50mM, 100mM, and 150mM) and different biogas slurry amounts (0g, 20g, 40g). CAT activity is highest at 0mM lead stress and generally decreases as salt stress increases. Within each salt stress level, higher biogas slurry amounts tend to enhance CAT activity, though the overall trend shows a decline in CAT activity as salt stress intensifies. At the highest lead stress level (150mM), CAT activity is the lowest across all biogas slurry treatments, suggesting that severe salt stress may overwhelm the plant's ant oxidative defenses despite the nutrient benefits of biogas slurry. This pattern highlights the complex interaction between nutrient supplementation and environmental stress in influencing plant biochemical responses.

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Figure 21- Effect of biogas slurry on CAT of mustard plant under salt stress

MDA

Maximum activity was detected in soybean crops when plants were treated with biogas slurry, with control level, enhanced the plant MDA activity under different cadmium stress levels. The results describe by that salt stress increase the plant MDA content which ultimately decrease MDA activity. Our results are in resemble with those that biogas slurry has shown effects on growth of different crop species under salt stress conditions.

Figure 22- Effect of biogas slurry on MDA of mustard plant under salt stress

H₂O₂

Maximum activity was detected in soybean crops when plants were treated with biogas slurry, with control level, enhanced the plant H₂O₂ activity under different

cadmium stress levels. The results describe by that salt stress increase the plant H_2O_2 content which ultimately decrease H_2O_2 activity. Our results are in resemble with those that biogas slurry has shown effects on growth of different crop species under salt stress conditions.

Figure 23- Effect of biogas slurry on H_2O_2 of mustard plant under salt stress

Discussion

Salt accumulation in the soil can significantly reduce growth parameters by disrupting the osmotic balance, preventing plants from germinating, and reducing water and nutrient uptake, which leads to toxicity. In this study, salt stress decreased the dry weight of mustard shoots and roots. In saline conditions, nutrient availability is often compromised due to excessive sodium ions, which interfere with nutrient uptake (Ehtaiwesh, 2022). The findings of this study are consistent with recent research on the use of organic amendments to alleviate salt stress. For example, a study by (Leogrande and Vitti, 2019) demonstrated that the application of organic matter, including compost and manure, improved soil nutrient content and plant growth under saline conditions. Similarly found that organic amendments enhanced soil structure and increased water retention, which are critical for plant health in saline soils (Farooqi *et al.*, 2023). By ensuring adequate water availability, biogas slurry helps maintain cellular functions and overall plant health (Kumar *et al.*, 2022a). Enhanced microbial activity makes more nutrients available to plants and produces substances that help plants tolerate stress, such as osmoprotectants and growth hormones (Gupta *et al.*, 2022). Thus, the improved microbial activity facilitated by biogas slurry indirectly supports better plant growth under saline conditions. This is supported by research from, who showed that organic amendments like biogas slurry boost soil microbial biomass and activity, leading to improved nutrient availability and plant growth (Abbas *et al.*, 2020).

Additionally, biogas slurry forms a protective rhizosphere around plant roots, enhancing the development of a beneficial microbial environment (Kumar *et al.*, 2022). This rhizosphere acts as a barrier against salt stress, buffering roots from high

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sodium concentrations and further supporting the plant's ability to cope with saline conditions. This concept is supported by research from (Farooqi *et al.*, 2023) who reported that organic amendments foster a beneficial rhizosphere environment that mitigates the adverse effects of salinity on plants. The protective effect of biogas slurry is further supported by its ability to enhance the activity of soil enzymes and increase the availability of growth-promoting hormone (Wang *et al.*, 2023). Moreover, biogas slurry application has been observed to improve the antioxidant defense system of plants. Under salt stress, plants generate reactive oxygen species (ROS). Biogas slurry enhances the activity of antioxidant enzymes such as superoxide dismutase (SOD), catalase (CAT), and peroxidase (POD), which neutralize ROS and protect plant cells from oxidative damage (Saleem *et al.*, 2025) This observation is in line with research by (Hoque *et al.*, 2022), which reported that organic amendments improve antioxidant enzyme activities, helping plants combat oxidative stress caused by salinity. Biogas slurry enhances chlorophyll content and photosynthetic rate, ensuring better light absorption and energy conversion in plants (Zhang *et al.*, 2025). This increased photosynthetic efficiency translates into higher biomass production and better overall growth, even under stressful saline conditions. Studies by (Hoque *et al.*, 2022) have shown that organic amendments can improve chlorophyll content and photosynthetic efficiency in salt-stressed plants, supporting better growth and productivity.

Therefore, the use of biogas slurry represents a sustainable and effective agricultural practice for mitigating the adverse effects of salt stress on crop growth (Kumar *et al.*, 2022a). Biogas slurry in managing salt stress. For example, research by (Saleem *et al.*, 2024) demonstrated that biogas slurry application significantly improved the growth and yield of wheat under saline conditions by enhancing nutrient uptake and reducing oxidative stress. As the demand for food production continues to rise and saline soils become more prevalent, adopting sustainable practices like biogas slurry application can help ensure agricultural productivity and food security (Wang *et al.*, 2023). Overall, this research adds to the growing body of evidence supporting the use of biogas slurry and other organic amendments as effective strategies for managing salt stress in crops. By improving soil fertility, enhancing nutrient availability and boosting plant resilience to stress, biogas slurry can play a crucial role in sustainable agriculture and cultivation of crops in saline-affected areas (Irin and Hasanuzzaman, 2024).

Conclusion

Salt stress is a major environmental pollutant that adversely affects plant growth in both terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems. The analysis revealed significant effects of both NaCl stress and biogas slurry on mustard growth parameters. Morphological attributes such as shoot and root length, leaf area, and the number of leaves per plant were significantly enhanced with the application of Biogas slurry despite increasing NaCl concentrations. At 0mM NaCl, all slurry treatments resulted in similar growth metrics. Physiologically, biogas slurry application increased chlorophyll a, chlorophyll b, total chlorophyll, and carotenoid contents, which are crucial for photosynthesis and overall plant health. Furthermore, the antioxidant enzyme activities, including superoxide dismutase (SOD), peroxidase (POD), and catalase (CAT), were

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significantly enhanced with biogas slurry application under salt stress conditions. The results of this study highlight the potential of biogas slurry as an effective growth promoter for maize under saline conditions. This research underscores the importance of optimizing biogas slurry application rates to maximize its benefits while mitigating salt stress in maize cultivation.

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